

PRACTICAL ANALYSIS OF THE PLACEMENT OF FILTHY ON THE SAME COTTON WOOL IN STACKS AND WAREHOUSES

Turgunov D.U., Kabilov B.Q.

Quality indicator practical analysis of the placement of the same cotton in garages and warehouses

Fergana Polytechnic Institute,

E-mail: dilmurodturgunov1992@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The article investigated whether raw material moisture is variable when storing cotton raw materials in Garam fields, and the effect of cotton on the degree of distribution of cotton in its layers cross section, depending on the height of the garam area. In this case, additional compaction of cotton under the influence of weight strength from the upper layers to the lower ones and differences in microneedles of cotton fibers have been found.

Keywords: Acorn, cotton, Acorn area, merchandiser, fiber, seeds, warehouse, dirt, moisture, density, weight, quality indicator.

Turgunov D.U., Kobulov B.Q.

Показатель качества практический анализ размещения же хлопка в бунта и на складах

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье изучено, что влажность сырья непостоянна при хранении хлопка на хлопкоочистительной площадке и ее влияние на уровень распределения хлопка в сечении слоев в зависимости от высоты хлопкоочистительной площадки. При этом определяли дополнительное уплотнение хлопка под действием силы тяжести от верхних слоев к нижним и различия микронейронных показателей хлопкового волокна.

Ключевые слова: хлопок, хлопок, хлопкоочистительная площадь, товаровед, волокно, семена, хранение, грязь, влажность, плотность, масса, показатель качества.

INTRODUCTION

It sells cotton raw materials grown by farms to a cotton textile cluster enterprise attached to the same khududud under contract. The cotton ginning enterprise wing in the cotton-textile cluster system and the cotton preparation facilities outside the enterprise operate. Cotton-making houses are divided into those under the enterprise, located outside the enterprise, depending on their location in relation to the enterprise. The preparatory settlement under korkhna is planned based on the total area of the enterprise, which will take on the Cotton of farms up to 15 km from the enterprise's territory. Off-Plant points, on the other hand, accept farmers' cotton, which is located more than 15 km away. The medium-sized cotton making point accepts up to 10,000 tons of cotton.

Depending on their location relative to the enterprise, cotton production facilities are divided into mas kans "under the enterprise" or "outside the enterprise". the training facilities under the enterprise are located in the common area of the kor room, where chama si is 15 km. accepts pax of farms, farmers, located in the distance. the cotton making mas kans outside the enterprise is 15 km. buys cotton from farms far away from

Cotton production facilities are separated into large, medium and small strength, depending on the volume of cotton adoption each season.

Large-capacity cotton production facilities have an area of 10,000 t. the average cotton making area is 6,000-10,000 t, while Cotton receives more than of cotton crop. up to, tiny mascans are usually 5000 t in their area. less than cotton is acceptable.

A special passport card is drawn up for a batch of cotton raw materials received. In the passport, the name of the breeder and industrial sortie of cotton, the number of stems, the weight of the available raw materials, the period of the ripening of acorns, the time of the beginning and completion of the batch, the last name of the responsible merchandiser are presented in the correct information.

Cotton fiber, the main raw material of the cotton cleaning enterprise, is divided into five sortes according to the state standard. According to the reception of cotton, it is divided by the commodity scientist into the corresponding varieties based on the appearance of cotton and places it in batches according to the fiber yield coefficient. Cotton making is separated into two or three zones in accordance with the instructions of the Executive Officer of the enterprise, and the merchandiser responsible for each zone is attached. In the part of the entrance.

Styles

Open stacks of 200, 250, 300, 350 and 400 tons per capacity variety, dirt and moisture are usually used to store hemp cotton. Closed piles are mainly used closed

piles of 750, 1,500, 3,000, 4,500 and 6,000 tons, made of crushed or raw brick, reinforced concrete structures. [1]

Figure 1. Drawing of a closed garm area

According to scientific studies studied, the density of the cotton layer in the garm fields has been found to increase over time.

In the lower layers of cotton in varieties III-IV-V, which are low when storing cotton in stacks, it has been observed that the fiber and pollen quality indicator change to negative state at a quick opportunity.

The surface of the Earth is paved with a thickness of 50 mm so that the cotton itself receives moisture quickly and does not receive moisture through the soil from groundwater when placing it on piles, since it is a quick-release material. When more than plan cotton is received at certain cotton atyorlov points, large stones with a surface area of 150 mm are plucked, between which they are teased with gravel or clay.

Geometric dimensions of open hem fields 25×14 , 22×11 , 11×10 m. At an average density of 200 kg/m^3 of cotton in these garms, it is possible to place 560 t of cotton in a $25 \times 14 \times 3$ meter Garam, and 380 tons of I, II and III varieties of cotton in a $22 \times 11 \times 8$ meter garm. In varieties I and II, a single tunnel is Dug along the width of the barrel, and in low varieties, a single tunnel is Dug along the length of the barrel at a distance of 5 m. the height of the tunnels should be 1.5 m, and the width should be 0.6 m. Cotton moisture is controlled through the air that a absorbent-type fan is generating from these tunnels. [2]

Figure 2. Drawing of open garm square

The density of cotton stored in open warehouses depends on its selection, variety, class and type of picking. Because seed varieties of cotton with seeds such indicators as dirt, moisture ensure an increase in density.

Scientific research shows that shortcomings are being observed in the dressing of open beds. As a result of this, when transferring cotton to production, there is a high porosity due to the fact that the garm does not break down, sufficiently leveling the layers. This creates complications such as the formation of additional garm fields in the storage of large amounts of cotton in the reception processes.

The elasticity property of the fiber resists the fact that the grafted cotton remains in the state of initial shibbalance during storage. Because the fiber has the strength of elasticity.

The porosity of the stored cotton is determined by the following formula:

(1)

In this case, the porosity of K-cotton in the mascara state, %,- the specific gravity of seed cotton, N/m^3 . At resolution = $1200n/M^3$ is obtained, g is the acceleration of free fall, m/s^2 ; -the density of the lumpy cotton in the mascara state, kg / m^3 . [3]

Due to the long storage time of the raw materials under production conditions, the weight force that a cotton gin gives from the top to the bottom, which has a certain yield, increases the density of cotton.

The uniformity of density in layers is inextricably linked with the type of cotton picking, industrial and breeding varieties, moisture levels and the forces of shibbalance during the period of grooming. The density of a layer of cotton with a height of up to 500 mm, which is poured in a Free State. Ya. It is possible to find by the Yampolsky formula:

, (2)

Where h is the layer height, mm; w is the moisture content of cotton, %;

Conclusion

1. When storing cotton raw materials received and obtained in Garam fields, it was found that the moisture values in the lower part are variable.

2. Differences in the degree of distribution of cotton were observed in its layer cross section, depending on the height of the garam area. In this, additional compaction of cotton was observed under the influence of weight strength, depending on the bottom from the upper layers.

3. A difference was observed in microneedle displays of cotton fibers with the same variety of Sanaot.

4. In the three different selection-related garam layers obtained for the experiment, the effect of the microneedle of the fiber on changes in densities depending on changes in height was determined in the analysis.

5. According to experimental tests, the density distribution in different layers and the industrial variety is the same as Andijan-35, Sultan,

Graphs of S-6524 breeding varieties with differences in microneedles were presented.

REFERENCES:

1. Khodzhiev M.T. Osnovi prosessa uplotneniya khlopka-Sirsa. Monograph. Izd. "Fan" Anne Rose. Tashkent, - 1996, - 144 P.
2. Khodzhiev M.T. Razrabotka teorii i obosnovanie parametrov mekhanizirovannogo tekhnologicheskogo prosessa minimodulnogo uplotneniya i skladirovaniya khlopka-Sirsa. Diss...D.t.n: - Tashkent, 1998,-318 P.
3. Pervichnaya pererabotka khlopka-Sirsa. Pod obtshey redaktsiey E.Z. Zikrièeva. Tashkent, "cocktail" -1999 g, P.49-50
4. Sarilakov O. Sh. The Change in Air Pressure Along the Length of the Pipeline Installation for Pneumatic Conveying of Raw Cotton. Journal Engineering and Technology/ 2016; 3(5): 89-92/http: // www. aascit. org/journal/et

5. D.U. Turgunov 1., O. Sh.Sarilakov2, N.M. Sattarov1. A study of the impact of the horizontal feeder on productivity as well as the quality of cotton // FarPI "Journal of Scientific Technology" STJ FerPI, FarPI ITJ, NTJ FerPI, 2021, T.25, №4. P.118-122
6. Obaydullayev, M. M. (2022). NEW DEFOLIANTS ARE A GUARANTEE OF PRODUCTIVITY. Archiv nauchnix issledovani, 2 (1).
7. Mo ' minjonović, U. M. (2022). Efficiency Of Defoliants. Eurasian Research Bulletin, 8, 9-12.
8. Mominjonović, U. M., & Ogley, M. I. V. (2022). STUDY AND ANALYSIS OF TECHNICAL PROCESSES OF COTTON DRYING IN A CLUSTER SYSTEM. International Journal of Advance Scientific Research, 2(11), 6-10.
9. Obaydullaev, M. M., & UT, T. (2022). DETERMINATION OF APPROPRIATE NORMS AND TERMS OF DEFOLIANTS. American Journal Of Applied Science And Technology, 2(05), 18-22.
10. Obaydullaev, M. M., & Makhmudova, G. O. (2022). MEDIUM FIBER S-8290 AND S-6775 COTTON AGROTECHNICS OF SOWING VARIETIES. European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies, 2(05), 49-54.
11. Obaydullaev, M. M., & Komilov, J. N. (2022). EFFECT OF DEFOLIANTS FOR MEDIUM FIBER COTTON. International Journal of Advance Scientific Research, 2(05), 1-5.
12. Obaydullaev, M. M., & Mahmutaliyev, I. V. (2022). EFFICIENCY OF FOREIGN AND LOCAL DEFOLIANTS ON THE OPENING OF CUPS. International Journal of Advance Scientific Research, 2(05), 6-12.
13. Obaydullaev, M. M., & Sultanov, S. T. (2022). DEFOLIATION IS AN IMPORTANT MEASURE. European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies, 2(05), 44-48.
14. Obaydullaev, M. M., & Nishanov, I. A. (2022). The Benefits of Defoliation. Eurasian Journal of Engineering and Technology, 6, 102-105.
15. Ubaydullayev is the son of Madaminzhan Mosinzhan, & Ma'rufzhonov is the son of Abdurahman Mosinzhan. (2022). BIOLOGICAL EFFICIENCY OF FOREIGN AND LOCAL DEFOLIANTS. "science and innovation" international scientific journal, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569808>
16. [THE INFLUENCE OF DEFOLIANTS ON THE TECHNOLOGICAL QUALITY INDICATORS AND CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF SEED](#)
M Ubaydullayev, U Kurbanova - Science and innovation, 2023
17. Ubaydullayev, M. M. (2022). YANGI DEFOLIANTLAR HOSILDORLIK GAROVI. Архив научных исследований, 2(1).

18. Mo‘minjonovich, U. M. (2022). Effectiveness Of Defoliant. Eurasian Research Bulletin, 8, 9-12.
19. Mominjonovich, U. M., & Ogli, M. I. V. (2022). STUDY AND ANALYSIS OF TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES OF COTTON DRYING IN A CLUSTER SYSTEM. International Journal of Advance Scientific Research, 2(11), 6-10.
20. Ubaydullaev, M. M., & UT, T. (2022). DETERMINATION OF APPROPRIATE NORMS AND TERMS OF DEFOLIANTS. American Journal Of Applied Science And Technology, 2(05), 18-22.